

THE ROLE OF OUTSIDE THE CLASSROOM ACTIVITIES IN DIRECTING STUDENTS TO PROFESSIONS

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the role of extracurricular activities in guiding schoolchildren to a profession, and in this process the teacher's pedagogical skills, knowledge and skills related to choosing a profession, as well as the age and knowledge of students according to the characteristics, the stages of orientation to the profession are given. Also, information is given on how foreign countries (Finland) conduct career guidance through extracurricular activities.*

Keywords: *young generation, education, career, career guidance, extracurricular activities, excursion, craft, observation, interest, age characteristics.*

The role of the school, which should prepare the young generation to actively participate in building a free and prosperous society, has increased more than ever in the era of rapid development of science and technology and social development. In this regard, it is an important task for the school at all stages of education and training to inculcate solid knowledge of the basics of science in students, to educate them with high consciousness, to form universal morality, to prepare the young generation for marriage and work, to consciously choose socially necessary professions.

Well, today in the education system, to what extent is it done by our primary school teachers, especially to arouse students' interest in the profession and to provide them with sufficient information about the world of professions? First of all, do our school teachers themselves have enough information about modern professions? Do they adequately guide students to the profession during the course of classes and extracurricular activities? questions arise. In order to get answers to these questions, we came to the following conclusion as a result of conducting surveys among our teachers working in the general education school today:

Today, most of the school teachers do not have enough information about modern professions emerging in the society and future promising professions.

Most of the teachers of the general education school did not regularly and systematically organize the work on the career guidance of the students during the lessons and outside of the lessons.

Some primary school teachers do not pay enough attention to the organization of various excursions, trips and cultural meetings to guide their students to the profession.

At this point, we should consider how important the right choice of profession is in a person's life. In fact, what factors have the most influence on the choice of a person's profession? In the course of our research, it became clear that today among our youth between the ages of 18 and 25, the following factors influenced them more when choosing their profession. (Fig. 1) It follows that the love of the profession is the leading factor in choosing that profession among most of our young people. Choosing the right profession is an important step in a person's life, the success of the entire life of the young generation largely depends on how correctly the profession is chosen. In order to choose the right profession according to the interests, inclinations, abilities

and opportunities of each student, it is necessary to take into account his health, mastery and emotions, which are most important in socially useful and productive work. ra is more resolved and manifested.[2]

Figure 1

Introduction to professions, trades and their secrets in the world, various crafts practiced by our ancient ancestors: painting, carpentry, wood carving, carving, crib making, knife making, coppersmithing, embroidery, shoemaking, hat making, introduction to professions such as goldsmithing, carpet making, crafting, weaving, jewelry, pottery is carried out in labor classes and extracurricular activities during the process of choosing a profession. Students' palaces, young technicians, young naturalists, young tourists' club and other extracurricular institutions are of great help in organizing students' extracurricular activities.[3] The main forms of extracurricular work are public works (events in school clubs, parties, debates and contests, organization of quizzes and exhibitions, excursions to nature, schools and museums), club work (participation of students in various clubs, sports sections, ensembles), independent activities (students' independent study outside the classroom, collection, technology, music, visual arts, drawing, etc.) can be shown. Work in this regard is carried out on the basis of a pre-arranged plan. "The right circles," wrote N. K. Krupskaya, "can make the matter of choosing a career for a teenager too easy." [4]

It is the need of the time to establish vocational training at the level of the educational reforms of our republic, to analyze and creatively apply the best practices gathered in this regard in our republic and developed foreign countries. How is the process of career orientation of students through extracurricular activities implemented in the Finnish education system?

In Finland, extracurricular activities are activities that exist outside the normal curriculum of a school or college, which must be done by students and range from 1st grade, high school, college to university available at all levels of education up to pre-school and many more. These activities differ mainly from voluntary and mandatory tasks. Benefits of extracurricular activities - these activities are important for both work and learning. Aside from books and e-learning,

another thing that helps promote well-rounded education is some key extracurricular activities, including basketball, baseball, drama, student government, choir, computer clubs, and more. These activities are believed to enhance peer communication and improve learners' time and stress management skills in the Finnish education system. Also choosing extracurricular activities as career choice-extracurricular activities like dance, art, acting, painting, singing, sports, cricket etc. can be the career choice of students [5]

Based on the above, we can say that it is effective to organize extracurricular activities into stages, taking into account their age and cognitive characteristics, to prepare students for independent career choice (Fig. 2).

Figure 2.

Conclusion: Today, in general secondary schools, the work of guiding students to the profession during extracurricular activities is based on the ability of the student to assess his own abilities, that is, on professions suitable for his interest. Having knowledge, information and understanding about the future of these professions is of great importance. In this case, taking into account the age characteristics of the students and guiding them to choose a profession step by step in the class section has a good effect. As a result, students who are about to graduate from

school will have deeply developed their professional inclination, abilities, knowledge and skills. This allows them to acquire one or more modern professions according to their chosen directions.

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